

Investigating the flavour development of scab-resistant Crimson Crisp apples

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Abstract

Apple scab is the most important apple disease in terms of economic aspects worldwide. Prevention is crucial, however, chemical or biological control are often uneconomic and time-consuming. To save resources, more and more scab-resistant varieties are bred, especially for cultivation in organic orchards. Fruit flavour is one of the most important properties for consumers. However, many scab resistant varieties lack pronounced apple flavour. The variety *Crimson Crisp* is reportedly on the same level or even higher when it comes to aroma, compared to traditional varieties. Nevertheless, to fully understand the aroma profile of this apple variety, an in-depth aroma profile analysis is needed. We investigated the formation of primary aroma compounds during on-tree maturation and ripening via headspace SPME-GC-MS measurements. In this contribution, we analyse its aroma profile and demonstrate the importance of long on-tree ripening of this promising scab-resistant apple variety. This will support the investigation of the optimal harvest conditions for *Crimson Crisp* and improve marketability of this highly ecological apple variety.

Keywords: apple, aroma, scab-resistant, Crimson Crisp, harvest

Introduction

According to the Food and Agricultural Organization of the United Nations apples are among the top three produced fruits worldwide, taking an overall share of 10 % of the total fruit production quantity for the year 2019 [1]. While banana and watermelon production are higher in overall quantities, apple production takes the top spot in Europe and North America. The versatility of the apple fruit is an essential factor for its popularity, as apples can be consumed raw, served as juices and smoothies as well as a part of sweet and salty meals.

Apples are produced in almost all parts of the world. However, the globalization of this industry also leads to problems. Apple scab is a common disease among the rose family (*Rosaceae*), which has been studied for more than 100 years. The disease, caused by the fungus *Venturia inaequalis*, is reported in almost all apple-producing areas. In terms of economic cost of control, apple scab is considered the most important apple disease worldwide [2].

The disease attacks both leaves and fruits [3]. Leaves may develop yellow to green spots on the upside and darker, sometimes velvety, spots on the lower surface. In more severe cases, the leaves also become twisted or wrinkled and might even drop in early summer. The symptoms on fruits are similar to those on leaves (Figure 1). Dark apple scab spots are deepened and may feature velvety spores in the centre. As these spores become bigger, the spots turn corky and fruits get deformed and have a risk of developing cracks on their surface. Severely infected fruits might drop at an early stage of their growing period.

Figure 1: Apples affected by apple scab.

Traditionally, the prevention of apple scab is a combination of sensible fungicide application as well as plant sanitation [4]. In recent years, producing apples labelled *certified organic*, *pesticide free*, or *integrated pest management* has been identified as a competitive advantage. Thus, the use of scab-resistant apple varieties is becoming more popular, particularly in organic orchards [5]. In 1943, a gene linked to apple scab resistance was discovered, the V_f gene. Although V_f has been described as the most abundant among apple scab resistant varieties in the last decades, nowadays more resistance genes and even more resistant varieties are known [6].

However, when it comes to breeding for new varieties, things are hardly ever straightforward. The target plant with the desired resistance gene often lacks palatable fruits. For example, the source of the V_f gene in *Crimson Crisp* dates five generations back [7]. This shows how much effort is necessary to meet consumer standards and to make farming and selling profitable.

The first seedling of *Crimson Crisp* (or *Coop 39*) was screened for scab-resistance in 1971 and the first fruits were observed in 1979 as part of a cooperative breeding program based in Illinois and New Jersey [7].

These midseason fruits are red, the texture, as the name already indicates, is very crisp. A consumer study in 2010 affirmed the very good flavour compared to both traditional and other scab resistant varieties [5]. However, to the best of our knowledge, an in-depth investigation of the aroma profile in Crimson Crisp apples has not been reported yet. On top, we follow the formation of the volatile aroma compounds from unripe fruits until early stages of senescence. We aim to evaluate the current harvest regimes on the basis of flavour development, since this variety is a rather new, but promising entry in Austrian organic orchards.

Experimental

Apple sampling

Crimson Crisp apples were handpicked in weekly intervals from apple plantations of the Research Centre for Fruit Growing & Viticulture, Graz-Haidegg, Austria. Sampling started on August 5th 2020, exactly 15 weeks after full blossom (wafb) (April 23rd 2020). Due to logistic reasons, the last two samples were taken in a 14-days interval, ending 27 wafb. After sampling, all apples were stored at room temperature in the dark over night until they were further processed. Primary aroma compounds were analysed from an enzyme inhibiting and antioxidant mixture containing approximately 75 g freshly cut and peeled apple pulp from 8-10 fruits, 75 mL deionised water, 30 g NaCl, 250 mg citric acid and 250 mg ascorbic acid. The resulting mixture was mixed in a commercial blender with a glass container to a purée and small amounts (ca. 4 mL) were frozen in glass vials at $-25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ until further use.

Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS) sample preparation and measurement

Aliquots of the homogenised samples (250 mg of purée) were transferred into headspace (HS) vials; 2-octanol was used as internal standard (30 ng absolute). Two replicates of each sample were prepared and analysed. After enrichment of the volatiles by HS-SPME (40 °C, 20 min, 50/30 µm DVB/CAR/PDMS fibre, 2 cm stable flex fibre) analyses were performed with 1-dimensional GC-MS (Shimadzu GCMS-QP 2010 Plus, Shimadzu Europa GmbH, Rxi[®] 5 ms, 30 m × 0.25 mm × 1 µm, Restek Corporation, USA, 35–350 amu, EI (70 eV)). Identification of the compounds was based on the comparison of the obtained mass spectra to those from MS libraries or authentic reference compounds as well as on retention indices (RI). Linear-temperature programmed RI were calculated using *n*-alkanes (C5-C26) and compared to data from authentic reference compounds and data from literature.

Data treatment

Data deconvolution was performed with PARADISE, based on the PARAFAC2 model [8]. The statistical analysis was performed with the MS Excel add-in XLSTAT. For the identification of significant differences between the samples and their ripening stages one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed ($p=0.05$). If statistically significant differences were observed within the data sets, the ANOVA was followed by post-hoc pairwise comparison using Tukey's Honestly Significant Difference (HSD) test control ($p < 0.05$) to check for differences between single samples. Correlations were analysed conducting a principal component analysis (PCA) using the Pearson correlation.

Results and discussion

In this study, we evaluated the flavour formation and, consequently, the current harvest recommendations for the scab resistant apple variety Crimson Crisp *via* HS-SPME-GC-MS aroma compound analysis. Since Crimson Crisp is primarily sold and consumed as fresh apple, we focused on the analysis of primary flavour compounds. In total, we identified 84 primary volatile compounds (33 esters, 25 carbonyl compounds, 17 alcohols, 9 others). All of these compounds have been described as part of the apple volatilome before. A total of 47 identified volatiles show a clear dependence of their concentrations on the ripening time on the tree. To demonstrate the development of the concentrations of the compound classes during on-tree ripening, six representative examples were selected and their concentrations are plotted in weekly intervals. For this purpose, two alcohols (2-methylbutanol, hexanol), two esters (2-methyl butylacetate, hexyl acetate) and two carbonyl compounds (pentanal and (*E*)-2-octenal) were selected (Figure 2). All these volatiles show odour activity values (OAV) higher than 1 (for alcohols and esters increasing values $20 < \text{OAV} < 150$, for aldehydes decreasing values between $0,5 < \text{OAV} < 5$). This demonstrates the relevance of these volatiles to the overall aroma of Crimson Crisp.

The current recommendations for the optimum harvest period of Crimson Crisp lay between the early to late middle of September [9]. This corresponds to 19-21 wafb in the agricultural area under investigation. However, following the development of the apple volatiles, the formation of compounds that are relevant for the apple flavour is clearly not at its maximum during this period. We observed an increase of 30 volatiles throughout 20-22 wafb, all of these compounds show a similar behaviour as the selected alcohols and esters (Figure 2). Many of these compounds are perceived as fruity, apple or floral notes and are well-known to contribute to the desirable overall flavour of apples. While alcohols and esters showed rising concentrations in 19-21 wafb, a maximum in concentrations was reached in 22-23 wafb for the observed alcohols; at that point the formation of the observed

esters was still not completed. In a previous study, a comparable behaviour was observed, showing that the delayed ester formation during on-tree ripening is primarily due to enhanced availability of alcohols as precursors compounds for esters, rather than enhanced AAT activities upon ripening [10]. On the contrary, aldehydes and ketones showed a steady concentration decrease during the observed period, which is demonstrated with the examples of pentanal and (*E*)-2-octenal (Figure 2). This decrease in concentration of carbonyl compounds is in accordance with findings described previously [10] where a steady decrease of LOX and HPL activities was observed during on-tree ripening in a comparable ripening period leading to lower amounts of LOX products in the fruits. Most aldehydes that were identified in Crimson Crisp apples are associated with green notes – consequently, their loss leads to a decrease of green flavour with a parallel increase of fruity, apple-like properties caused by the reported formation of esters and alcohols.

Figure 2: The concentrations [$\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$] of six representative volatiles in Crimson Crisp pulp over the course of maturation and ripening on the tree in weeks after full blossom (wafb) [w]; concentration of alcohols and esters refer to the left-hand side y-axis, those of aldehydes to the right-hand side y-axis.

Principal component analysis (PCA) was applied to better visualise the correlations between the concentrations of the apple volatiles and the harvest date of the Crimson Crisp fruits (Figure 3). For this purpose, volatile compounds, which did not show concentration dependence on the on-tree development of the fruits were not included in the principal component analysis in order to facilitate interpretation and to keep the focus on compounds related to the on-tree ripening process. Forty-seven volatiles (55 % of the total volatilome) were included. The biplot given in Figure 3 shows 180° counter-clockwise behaviour of the on-tree ripening times from the border of quadrants II and III to the border between quadrants I and IV. The unripe fruits harvested after 15-17 wafb are closely correlated to volatiles with green, grassy unripe sensory attributes (mainly aldehydes, green dots in Figure 3) as well as ketones with mushroom-like and metallic attributes such as for example 1-octen-3-one. On the other hand, apples harvested 22-27 wafb are highly correlated with a large group of esters and several alcohols.

Figure 3: Biplot of the principal component analysis (PCA) based on 47 volatiles in Crimson Crisp apples and the harvest dates. Weeks after full blossom (wafb) (black squares), esters (red dots), alcohols (purple dots), aldehydes (green dots), ketones (yellow dots) and others (grey dots).

Conclusion

Our findings demonstrate that Crimson Crisp apples show strong flavour formation upon on-tree ripening. According to the current harvest recommendations, the apples are harvested long before the maximum formation of compounds that are relevant for the flavour formation. Based on our finding, we propose a shift of the recommended harvest period from 19-21 wafb to 22-25 wafb, to fully develop the flavour of Crimson Crisp apples. Although this leads to storage of fruits with an unusually high starch degradation index of > 8.0 . Early experiments show good storage stability of Crimson Crisp apples harvested 23 wafb. With these results, we demonstrate the importance of flavour analysis for agricultural purposes for the optimisation of flavour properties of domestic agricultural crop.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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